

PACIFIC RISCC MANAGEMENT NETWORK

MANAGING INVASIVE SPECIES IN A CHANGING PACIFIC

2025

**SURVEY OF NATURAL RESOURCE MANAGERS IN
HAWAI'I AND THE US-AFFILIATED PACIFIC ISLANDS**

ABOUT THIS REPORT

The survey and analysis described in this report were carried out by the Pacific Regional Invasive Species and Climate Change Management Network (Pacific RISCC) Core Team under Arizona State University's Institutional Review Board (STUDY00022121). The Pacific RISCC Core Team is made up of representatives from the institutions below.

Recommended citation: Brewington L., Parsons E., Martin C., Daehler C. 2025. Managing Invasive Species in a Changing Pacific: Survey of Natural Resource Managers in Hawai'i and the US-Affiliated Pacific Islands. Honolulu: The Pacific Regional Invasive Species and Climate Change Management Network. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17782605>

Cover image: University of Hawai'i at Hilo professor and graduate student conducting native tree surveys at Pu'uwa'awa'a State Forest Reserve on Hawai'i Island. Credit: Elliott Parsons

This page: The University of Guam Conservation Corps plants tree seedlings across Guam to protect the island's watersheds against erosion and ensure sustainable water supplies. Credit: Laura Brewington

Back cover: Members of the Pacific RISCC Management Network visit James Campbell National Wildlife Refuge in Hawai'i to observe seabird recovery efforts and the benefits of invasive mammal exclusion. Credit: James Campbell National Wildlife Refuge

INVASIVE SPECIES & CLIMATE CHANGE

BACKGROUND

Ecosystem health across Hawai'i and the U.S.-Affiliated Pacific Islands (USAPI) is threatened by two interacting stressors: invasive species and climate change[1]. Global movement of goods and people accelerates introductions and spread, while climate shifts alter establishment success, impacts, and management windows for invaders[2]. Pacific Island communities and ecosystems also face high exposure to sea-level rise, ocean and air warming, shifting rainfall, coastal flooding, and cyclone hazards that jointly affect biodiversity, water security, food systems, and culturally important resources[3]. These pressures can expand suitable ranges for invasive species, intensify their impacts, and complicate control—particularly during and after extreme events—underscoring the need for climate-informed management.

Because managers often operate at local scales while drivers and information span jurisdictions, boundary organizations have been created to bridge the gap between information producers and end users[4]. The Pacific RISCC, part of a growing national RISCC network[5], links researchers and practitioners to co-produce actionable knowledge, align priorities, and address barriers such as limited time, funding, personnel, and access to usable climate information. Together, these efforts help translate emerging science into resilient, island-appropriate prevention, early detection and rapid response (EDRR), and long-term control strategies. Nevertheless, as the dual threats of invasive species and climate change continue to interact and intensify, natural resource manager needs are also evolving and entities like Pacific RISCC must continually refine their goals and activities to meet them.

This report summarizes the findings from a 2025 survey of natural resource managers in Hawai'i and the USAPI that was designed to measure their level of concern about the influence of climate change on invasive species management, compare their access to and understanding of existing climate information for the region, and identify barriers to success in incorporating climate change into management practices. The survey questionnaire (Appendix) was adapted from a prior survey instrument that Pacific RISCC conducted in 2020 to establish a baseline of the needs of Hawai'i-based natural resource managers. Survey questions were also designed to closely match surveys used by several of the other RISCC teams and described in Evans et al. 2025[4]. This study was carried out under Arizona State University's Institutional Review Board (STUDY00022121) and the survey was distributed online through the Pacific RISCC listserv and other partner lists in early 2025.

ABOUT PACIFIC RISCC

A REGIONAL KNOWLEDGE-SHARING NETWORK

The Pacific RISCC Management Network was founded in 2019 to increase Pacific Island resilience to the interacting threats of climate change and invasive species by integrating climate change science and adaptation with natural resources management and invasive species control, prevention, and research. As a boundary organization, Pacific RISCC connects scientists and resource managers to reduce the combined risks of climate change and invasive species across Hawai'i and the U.S.-Affiliated Pacific Islands. Led by a Core Team and a Science Advisory Team and made up of an active community of nearly 600 members across the region, the network convenes partners to share needs, synthesize knowledge, and co-produce actionable research and guidance tailored to island contexts. Pacific RISCC emphasizes practical, manager-ready programming. The network hosts webinars, peer exchanges, and regional symposia and workshops.

Recent activities include a forum at the Hawai'i Conservation Conference on lessons learned from climate-related disasters in the Pacific Islands region and a 2025 webinar featuring the Hawai'i Invasive Species Council to showcase collaborative, cross-agency approaches to prevent and manage invasions. Brief research summaries that translate new studies into key takeaways for decision makers are sent out to the network on a regular basis.

Strategically, Pacific RISCC aligns its efforts with regional biosecurity plans and adaptation priorities and with the broader RISCC Network across the United States and Canada. By linking local practitioners with research and regional policy conversations, Pacific RISCC helps translate emerging science into actionable strategies to improve resilience through prevention, early detection and rapid response, and long-term control of invasive species, suited to Pacific Island contexts and geographies.

SUMMARY OF KEY FINDINGS

RESPONDENT BACKGROUND AND DEMOGRAPHICS

- Most respondents worked in academia (31%) or were federal or state agency employees (42%) with more than 10 years of experience working in natural resources management and/or invasive species (65%). The majority (55%) are invasive species managers, with remaining respondents working in research, outreach, and regulatory aspects.
- Respondents worked at many sites, or networks of sites, within a single state/island (39%) or region (41%), that were spread out widely across Hawai'i and the USAPI. Slightly more than half worked in Hawai'i, while the remainder (45%) worked in the US Pacific Territories and Freely Associated States, as well as Papāhānaumokuākea Marine National Monument.
- Management priority areas were most commonly biodiversity, endangered species, and cultural resources. Tourism and game management were the least common.

PERSPECTIVES ABOUT MANAGING INVASIVE SPECIES UNDER A CHANGING CLIMATE

- Managing for invasive species was overall more important than considering climate change. Still, 70% of respondents said it was important or very important for them to consider climate change in their management priorities, and almost 100% assigned the same importance to managing for invasive species.
- Respondents reported high levels of concern (58% were very concerned) about the impacts of climate change on invasive species management.

PERCEPTIONS AND USE OF CLIMATE INFORMATION

- More than 80% of respondents said they used climate information regularly or at least occasionally.
- Climate change information was primarily transferred person-to-person, rather than through the published literature, and it most frequently came from informal conversations and management documents, as opposed to online tools and data sources.
- Almost all respondents at least occasionally obtained information about climate change from meetings and workshops or web-based materials. Materials from extension agents or programs, case studies, and model outputs were the least likely to be utilized, however.
- When asked how satisfied they are with the quality, relevance, and number of existing products produced by climate researchers (such as technical reports, publications, websites, or tools), few respondents reported being very satisfied. More than a third reported that they were satisfied with what was available, however. Ten percent were not satisfied at all with the relevance of products to their work, and a fair number of respondents also said they did not know or had no opinion about the quality (15%), relevance (13%), or number (18%) of available products.

LIMITATIONS TO MANAGING INVASIVE SPECIES UNDER A CHANGING CLIMATE

- For more than half of all respondents, agency mandates and personnel were always perceived limiting factors when it came to both managing for invasive species and incorporating climate change into management practices.
- Respondents reported more serious issues with the availability of information when incorporating climate into management practices, compared to the availability of information for invasive species management alone.

DECISION-MAKING NEEDS: KNOWLEDGE, PRODUCTS, AND SERVICES

- When asked what climate information products they needed to better manage invasive species under a changing climate, more than 75% of respondents identified better climate projections at relevant scales. Desired temporal scales for management: seasonal to 10 years or less. Desired spatial scales for management: watershed and landscape.
- More than half of respondents also expressed a desire for a collaborative research project, better communication of what climate information is available, more information on the appropriateness of the available data products, and better access to data outputs.
- The highest priorities for climate research topics were range shifting species, the resilience of native ecosystems, and changes to wet and dry seasons. The efficacy of chemical and mechanical control methods were the lowest priorities.

RESPONDENT BACKGROUND & DEMOGRAPHICS

ORGANIZATION TYPE AND FOCAL REGION

Respondents were asked approximately how many years they have worked in natural resource/invasive species management, and what type of institute or agency do they work for, as well as the part of the Pacific Islands region in which they conduct most of their work.

Most respondents were federal (23%), state (19%), or academic (31%) employees with more than 10 years of experience (65%). Individuals who worked for other government institutions (including other national or territorial governments), NGOs, and the industry/private sector made up about a quarter (27%) of all respondents.

Figure 1. Organization type (left) and number of years of experience (right), N=110*

Many survey respondents (41%) worked across a network of sites in multiple states and/or islands (Figure 2, next page). Another 39% worked across multiple sites within a single state or island. Only 11% worked within a single site. A large percentage worked statewide in Hawai'i (21%), while 34% worked specifically in the counties of Hawai'i (14%), Maui (8%), Honolulu (8%), and Kaua'i (4%). Another 45% worked within the USAPI (the US territories of Guam, the Commonwealth of the Northern Mariana Islands, and American Sāmoa, and the Freely Associated States of Palau, the Federated States of Micronesia, and the Republic of the Marshall Islands). Three percent worked within Papāhanaumokuākea Marine National Monument.

*There were 110 total respondents to the survey. Respondents were not required to answer all questions and the total number of responses per question (N) ranged from 85 to 110. The total number of respondents per question is provided with each figure caption.

Figure 2. Scale of work site (left) and region, state, or county where most work is conducted (right), N=108

When asked how they most commonly interacted with invasive species, 55% reported that they managed invasive species, whereas 19% conducted invasive species research and 11% engaged in outreach. An additional 11% were involved in regulatory aspects of invasive species work or “other” activities.

Figure 3. Primary interactions with invasive species, N=110

Figure 4. Current management priority areas, N=97

The most commonly selected management priority area was biodiversity (76%) followed by endangered species (69%) and cultural resources (46%). Many respondents selected multiple categories. Marine resources, tourism, and game management were least represented and were selected by 24%, 14%, and 10% of respondents, respectively. More federal agency respondents worked in endangered species (20%), biodiversity (23%), and rare habitats (14%). Similarly, NGO workers more frequently managed endangered species (19%), biodiversity (20%), and cultural resources (15%).

Respondents who worked in academia were equally likely to be involved in agriculture (16%), biodiversity (17%), and endangered species (16%). Both the industry/private sector (21%) and other government respondents (33%) more commonly reported working in forestry.

PERSPECTIVES ABOUT MANAGING INVASIVE SPECIES UNDER A CHANGING CLIMATE

Respondents were asked to rank how important managing invasive species was to them in accomplishing their management goals on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 indicated not important and 5 indicated very important (blue bars, Figure 5). Not surprisingly, a large majority (85%) said that it was very important, with the remaining 15% saying it was at least moderately important.

They were then asked how important considering climate change was to them in accomplishing their management goals (orange bars, Figure 5). About half (48%) responded that it was very important, with only 8% reporting that it was mildly important. None of the respondents rated either of these management aspects as not important.

Figure 5. Importance of managing invasive species (blue bars, N=99) and considering climate change in accomplishing management goals (orange bars, N=98)

Respondents were also asked how concerned they were about how climate change might complicate invasive species management. Fifty-eight percent reported being very concerned and all but a small minority (5%) said that they were at least moderately concerned.

Figure 6. Level of concern about how climate change might complicate invasive species management, N=98

When analyzed by organization, respondents from NGOs and all three government agency categories (US federal, state, and other government) assigned the highest levels of importance to considering climate change when managing invasive species (Figure 7, next page). The three government agency categories again assigned the highest level of concern about how climate change could affect their invasive species management. Academic respondents assigned a higher level of concern to the effects of climate change than their NGO and industry counterparts, however, and overall, industry respondents reported lower levels of both importance and concern about climate change with respect to invasive species management. None of the respondents assigned the lowest level (1) of importance or concern to either survey question.

Figure 7. Level of importance in considering climate change (top) and level concern about climate change impacts on invasive species management (bottom) by agency

67%
OF TIME MANAGING
EXISTING INVASIVES

33%
OF TIME PREPARING
FOR NEW INVASIONS

Respondents were asked approximately what percentage of their work time they spend 1) managing existing invasive species (e.g., removal, containment, or monitoring), versus 2) preventing, managing, or planning for emerging or horizon invasive species (e.g. invasive species with a high risk of introduction). On average, respondents reported spending around 67% of their time managing existing invasive species (N=98), compared to preventing, managing, or planning for new species (33%, N=89).

Figure 10. Frequency of use of different types of climate information resources, N=87

When asked how satisfied they are with the quality, number, and relevance of existing products produced by climate researchers (such as technical reports, publications, websites, or tools), less than 10% of respondents reported being very satisfied. However, more than a third responded that they were satisfied with what is available.

Ten percent were not satisfied at all with the relevance of products to their work, and a fair number of respondents also said they did not know or had no opinion about the quality (15%), number (18%), or relevance (13%) of available products.

Figure 11. Level of satisfaction about the quality, number, and relevance of climate information products, N=86

LIMITATIONS TO MANAGING INVASIVE SPECIES UNDER A CHANGING CLIMATE

Respondents were asked to indicate how severely a set of factors limited their ability to manage invasive species (blue bars, Figure 12). A large majority (81%) of respondents indicated that agency mandates were frequently a limiting factor and personnel (75%) followed closely behind. Information availability/access (67%), available tools to prioritize actions (49%), and funding (41%) were cited as occasionally being limiting factors for achieving invasive

species management goals. For each factor, less than 20% of respondents indicated that they presented no limitations at all.

Respondents were asked the same question again, but with respect to incorporating climate change into management activities, and response patterns were similar (orange bars, Figure 12). Personnel (59%) and agency mandates (58%) were again cited the most as being limiting factors often or always. About half of respondents indicated that information availability/access, funding, and available tools to prioritize actions occasionally presented difficulties. Once again, fewer than 20% of respondents stated that these factors posed no limitations to their ability to incorporate climate change into management actions.

Figure 12. How severely various factors limited respondents' abilities to manage invasive species (blue bars, N=86) and incorporate climate change into management (orange bars, N=85)

DECISION-MAKING NEEDS: KNOWLEDGE, PRODUCTS, AND SERVICES

When asked about their decision-making needs, respondents identified several types of knowledge, products, and services that they would like to receive from the climate information community to better support their decisions. Three-quarters of respondents said that more climate projections over a range of scales (such as rainfall projections at the refuge-to-island scale) would be useful.

Figure 13. Types of products and information desired from the climate science community, N=85

Nearly 70% identified collaborative research projects and 58% selected better communication about the information that is available as an opportunity to support decision making. About half of respondents expressed a desire for more information on the appropriateness of the available data products, better access to data outputs, and a better understanding of uncertainty in climate projections. Having a better understanding of climate science technical aspects was selected by only 34% of respondents. There were also write-in in responses, which included a request for commitments to update climate information materials on a regular basis and management guidelines to apply to conservation and restoration practices immediately.

Respondents were asked to rank different temporal and spatial scales of climate information based on how important they are for management. Having climate projections at adequate and meaningful scales was very important to survey respondents. The top ranked temporal scale for decision-making was seasonally, and the lowest ranked temporal scale was 50-100 years, followed by the next longest temporal scale of 25-50 years. These, unfortunately, are precisely the scales of most of the existing climate projections for Hawai'i and the USAPI. For spatial scale, respondents identified the watershed as being the most important for managing invasive species under a changing climate. The largest spatial scales (state, archipelago, and region) were ranked the lowest, which again reflected the scales of most of the available climate projections.

Figure 14. Rankings of priority temporal (top) and spatial (bottom) scales for climate information, N=72

When asked to rate potential climate-related research topics as priorities for management actions, respondents most often ranked range shifting species (67%), the resilience of native ecosystems (63%), and changes to wet and dry seasons (61%) as high priorities. About half of respondents also ranked biocontrol efficacy, new invasion pathways, and changing invasive species impacts as high priorities. About half of respondents also ranked sleeper species as a medium priority topic. The lower priority topics included chemical and mechanical control efficacy (22% and 26%, respectively).

Figure 15. Rankings of selected climate-related research topics and importance for management action, N=82

Respondents were asked to write in any activities or topics of interest on invasive species and climate change that they would like Pacific RISCC to consider. Of the 22 responses, four referred to species- or ecosystem-specific focus areas, such as marine invasive species or invasive mammal control; three referred to biocontrol and management tools for pests like coconut rhinoceros beetle and vines; and three referred to ecosystem and native species impacts. Remaining responses reflected a desire for more capacity building and outreach, collaboration and information sharing, research and innovation, and more.

Figure 16. Write-in responses expressing desired activities or topics of interest for Pacific RISCC to consider, summarized by theme, N=22

The survey concluded by asking respondents whether they had participated in Pacific RISCC's baseline survey from 2020, which was only distributed to Hawai'i-based natural resource managers. Only a few (8%) responded "yes," but almost half said they did not know and another 45% said they had not. Lastly, respondents were asked how long they had been members of the Pacific RISCC network and listserv, and the majority (almost 75%) had been members for more than one year. Twenty-one percent were not members, and only 10% had recently joined the network.

Figure 17. Whether respondents completed the 2020 survey of Hawai'i-based natural resource managers (left) and how long respondents have been members of the Pacific RISCC network (right), N=86

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The Pacific RISCC team is grateful to all survey respondents and those who helped distribute the survey beyond the members of the Pacific RISCC listserv. The survey was carried out under Arizona State University's Institutional Review Board (STUDY00022121). Funding in support of the survey design, analysis, and writeup was from the US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration award NA21OAR4310308, and the US Geological Survey Pacific Islands Climate Adaptation Science Center and the US Fish and Wildlife Service, Region 1 Science Applications Cooperative Agreement #G23AC00648.

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APPENDIX: SURVEY

SURVEY QUESTIONS

1. Approximately how many years have you worked in natural resource management?
 - < 2 years
 - 2-5 years
 - 6-10 years
 - 10+ years
 - I don't work in natural resources management.
 2. Approximately how many years have you worked with invasive species?
 - < 2 years
 - 2-5 years
 - 6-10 years
 - 10+ years
 - I don't work with invasive species.
 3. In your current position, your interactions with invasive species occur primarily through:
 - Invasive species management
 - Invasive species research/science
 - Invasive species outreach/community education
 - Regulatory (permitting, quarantine, inspection, policy, etc.)
 - I don't work with invasive species.
 - Other (please describe):
 4. The institute/organization where you work is best described as:
 - Academia/University
 - Non-governmental organization
 - Industry/Corporate/Private sector
 - National/Territorial/Tribal/First Nation government
 - City/Municipal government
 - County government
 - State government
 - US Federal government
 - Other (please describe):
 5. What is the scale of the sites where you work?
 - Single site
 - Network of sites within a single state or island
 - Multi-state or multi-island network of sites
 - National network of sites
 - Other (please describe):
-

6. Please select the region/county/state in which you conduct most of your work. Select all that apply:

- American Sāmoa
- Commonwealth of the Northern Mariana Islands
- Federated States of Micronesia
- Guam
- Hawai'i - state-wide
- Hawai'i - Hawai'i County
- Hawai'i - Honolulu County
- Hawai'i - Kaua'i County
- Hawai'i - Maui County
- Hawai'i - Papahānaumokuākea Marine National Monument
- Republic of the Marshall Islands
- Republic of Palau
- Other:

7. What are your management priorities in your current position? Select all that apply:

- Agriculture/Aquaculture
- Biodiversity
- Cultural resources
- Endangered species
- Forestry
- Freshwater resources
- Game management
- Marine resources
- Rare habitats
- Tourism/Recreation
- Other:

8. How important is considering climate change in accomplishing your management goals?

Not important 1 2 3 4 5 Very important

9. How important is managing invasive species in accomplishing your management goals?

Not important 1 2 3 4 5 Very important

10. How concerned are you about how climate change might complicate invasive species management?

Not at all concerned 1 2 3 4 5 Very concerned

11. Of the time I spend focused on invasive species, I spend _____ % of my time managing EXISTING invasive species (i.e., removal, containment, monitoring of invasive species currently present).

12. Of the time I spend focused on invasive species, I spend _____ % of my time preventing, managing, or planning for EMERGING (new) or HORIZON invasive species (i.e., invasive species with a high risk of introduction).

13. List the top invasive species (up to 5) that you expect will pose the greatest threat to your organization's management goals in the next 5-10 years.

14. How would you rank your knowledge/use of regional or state-level climate information?

- No knowledge/use
- Heard of it but never used it
- Used once or twice in my work
- Used regularly in my work
- Other (please describe):

15. How often do you use the following types of climate information resources to inform invasive species management? Choices: Not at all, Occasionally, Frequently, N/A

- Peer-reviewed literature
- Management documents, technical reports
- Grey literature (e.g., agency plans)
- Meetings, workshops, or symposia
- Listservs, websites, or online tools
- Extension materials from Land Grant institutions
- Best practices/Lessons learned
- Case studies
- Models (e.g., atmospheric, ecosystem, climate, economic)
- Spatial data
- Land cover and use data
- Informal conversations with experts and colleagues
- Knowledge from stakeholders or community members
- Other (please describe):

16. How satisfied are you with the quality, number, and relevance of data products, reports, websites, or tools produced by regional climate researchers? Choices: No opinion/don't know, Not at all satisfied, Somewhat satisfied, Satisfied, Very satisfied

- Quality of products
 - Number of products
 - Relevance of products to your work
-

17. Please indicate how severely the following factors limit your ability to manage invasive species. Choices: Not at all, Sometimes, Often, Always

- Information availability/access
- Agency mandates
- Tools or processes to prioritize actions
- Funding
- Personnel
- Other (please describe):

18. Please indicate how severely the following factors limit your ability to incorporate climate change into management actions. Choices: Not at all, Sometimes, Often, Always

- Information availability/access
- Agency mandates
- Tools or processes to prioritize actions
- Funding
- Personnel
- Other (please describe):

19. What would you like from climate information producers? Select all that apply:

- Climate projections over a range of spatial scales (rainfall projections at the refuge to island-scale, for example)
- Better understanding of uncertainty in the projected future conditions, and how to deal with it
- Better understanding of the technical aspects of climate science
- Better access to data outputs for particular applications
- More information on the appropriateness of data outputs for particular applications at particular timelines
- Better communication of what information is and isn't available
- A collaborative research project to help answer specific questions, such as predicted impacts on specific species
- Other (please describe):

20. What timescales are the most crucial to have climate projections for, to manage your natural resources optimally? [rank from highest priority (top) to lowest priority (bottom)]

- Seasonally
- Annually
- 1-10 years
- 10-25 years
- 25-50 years
- 50-100 years

21. What spatial scales are the most crucial to have climate projections for, to manage your natural resource optimally? [rank from highest priority (top) to lowest priority (bottom)]

- Watershed scale
- Landscape scale
- Island scale
- State scale
- Archipelago scale
- Regional scale

22. Please rate the following climate-related research topics for their importance in your management actions. Choices: Low priority, Medium priority, High priority

- Resilience of native communities: Identifying areas less vulnerable to climate change and/or invasion (e.g., refugia)
- Range shifting species and hotspots of future invasion
- Wet and dry season changes
- Changing impacts
- Sleeper species: Identifying species that are currently naturalized but could become invasive with climate change
- New pathways of introduction
- Changes in extreme events
- Biocontrol efficacy: Assessing whether the efficacy of biocontrol agents will change with climate change
- Chemical control efficacy: Assessing whether the efficacy of chemical control methods (e.g. timing, amounts) will change with climate change
- Mechanical control efficacy: Assessing whether the efficacy of mechanical control methods (e.g. timing, frequency) will change with climate change
- Other (please describe):

23. Did you complete the Pacific RISCC survey of Hawai'i-based natural resource managers in 2020?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

24. How long have you been a member of the Pacific RISCC network (e.g., receiving information from the listserv, using resources, attending activities)?

- Not a member
- < 1 year
- 1 - 3 years
- > 3 years

25. Please suggest any activities or topics of interest on invasive species and climate change for Pacific RISCC to consider.

26. Please provide any additional feedback on this survey.
